

A Study on the Relationship Between Smartphone Addiction, Trait Anger and Anger Expression Styles in Adolescents

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Abstract

This study examined the relationships between smartphone addiction, trait anger and anger expression styles among adolescents. The research employed a relational survey design and included 713 high school students from various types of secondary schools in Mersin, Türkiye, during the 2023–2024 academic year. Data were collected using the Smartphone Addiction Scale–Short Version and the Trait Anger and Anger Expression Scale (STAXI) along with a demographic information form. Pearson correlation analyses revealed significant relationships between smartphone addiction and all subdimensions of anger. Specifically, smartphone addiction was positively correlated with trait anger, anger-in, and anger-out, while negatively correlated with anger control. These findings suggest that as adolescents' smartphone addiction levels increase, their trait anger and maladaptive anger expression tendencies rise, whereas their ability to anger control decreases. The results are discussed within the framework of emotional regulation and behavioral addiction theories, emphasizing the potential psychological risks associated with excessive smartphone use during adolescence. Implications for preventive education and counseling practices are also presented.

Keywords: Adolescents, anger expression styles, correlation, smartphone addiction, trait anger

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary era, technology has developed at an extraordinary pace, influencing individuals across physical, social, cultural and psychological dimensions. Among the most significant technological innovations of our time are smartphones. In 2023, the proportion of households in Türkiye possessing a smartphone reached 99.7%, meaning that nearly every household owns at least one device (Turkish Statistical Institute, 2024).

In recent years, smartphones have become an integral part of daily life, and their influence on adolescents—who are in a developmental stage characterized by high sensitivity to external stimuli—has been increasing rapidly. Studies indicate that smartphones are more appealing to adolescents than to adults and that their rate of use is also considerably higher among this age group (Wen et al., 2023). Adolescence, while critical for identity and personality development, is also a period associated with heightened risk-taking, sensation seeking, increased depressive moods, and a strong need for belonging to an ideology or group (Ektiricioğlu et al., 2020). It has been reported that adolescents are often cognitively unprepared to navigate the complex world of the internet, struggle to access accurate information, and are thus more vulnerable to its adverse influences (Tarı Cömert & Kayıran, 2010). Research also indicates that adolescents tend to avoid being separated from their smartphones, feel a constant need to check them, carry them everywhere, and experience difficulty focusing on their immediate environment when away from their devices. Excessive engagement with smartphones can hinder concentration on academic tasks, consequently reducing academic performance (Gümüş & Ögeve, 2015). Behaviors such as restlessness and irritability when separated from a smartphone are considered withdrawal symptoms, resembling those observed in other types of addiction (Chou & Chou, 2019).

Smartphone addiction can be defined as the uncontrollable overuse of smartphones to the extent that it adversely affects daily functioning (Park & Lee, 2012). It is characterized by behaviors such as an inability to stay away from the device for extended periods, feelings of tension or discomfort when deprived of it, and frequent checking (Kalender, 2021). The convenience of constant accessibility and the high degree of usability have significantly increased the risk of addiction. Research suggests that one in four adolescent uses their

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smartphone in a manner consistent with behavioral addiction (Sohn et al., 2019). A meta-analysis examining smartphone addiction among adolescents found prevalence rates ranging between 39% and 44% (Davey & Davey, 2014).

In Türkiye, 96.7% of individuals aged 16–24 owned a mobile phone and 82.6% used the internet in 2021; the average time spent on social media ranged between 2 hours 44 minutes and 2 hours 54 minutes per day (TÜİK, 2021; 2022a; 2022b). Another study conducted in Türkiye found that nearly 50% of adolescents reported using their phones for at least four hours a day and that there was a significant positive correlation between smartphone addiction and loneliness (Çakır & Oğuz, 2017). Other research has shown that smartphone addiction among adolescents is positively associated with depression, aggression, anxiety, alcohol and tobacco use, hypertension, obesity, and poor sleep quality (Akaltun, 2020; Akaltun & Ayaydın, 2019; Dikeç et al., 2020; Seo, 2018; Zou et al., 2019). Conversely, negative relationships have been observed between smartphone addiction and constructs such as self-esteem, self-confidence, academic achievement, and self-control (Amez & Bearth, 2020; Chen et al., 2023; Mazılı & Gültekin, 2020; Şar, 2013). As expected, smartphone addiction in adolescents correlates positively with negative psychological variables and negatively with positive ones. Notably, there are no existing studies in Türkiye examining the relationship between smartphone addiction and trait anger and anger expression styles among adolescents.

Trait anger refers to the frequency and intensity with which an individual experiences anger (Saçar, 2007). It reflects both the level at which anger is experienced and its emotional impact on the individual (Albayrak, 2009). Individuals with high levels of trait anger experience anger more frequently and intensely than those with lower levels (Spielberger et al., 1995). Trait anger can be quantified and conceptualized not as a temporary state but as a personality disposition indicating one's tendency to become angry (Deffenbacher, 1999). Individuals with high trait anger are more likely to express anger destructively, whether verbally or physically, and often experience interpersonal conflicts, whereas those with lower trait anger tend to express anger in healthier ways, maintaining more positive relationships (Thomas, 2007). Considering the developmental characteristics of adolescence, a high level of trait anger may lead to various negative outcomes during this period.

Anger expression styles are typically categorized as anger-in (internalized anger), anger-out (externalized anger), and anger control (Spielberger et al., 1995). Anger-in refers to suppressing or internalizing anger rather than expressing it outwardly (Karataş, 2009; Saçar, 2007; Spielberger et al., 1995). Individuals with this style tend to avoid direct confrontation, expressing anger indirectly through behaviors such as sulking or withdrawal (Özer, 1994a). They may believe that expressing anger could lead to retaliation or exacerbate conflicts (Brondolo et al., 1997). Prolonged suppression of anger is considered maladaptive, as it may manifest through psychosomatic symptoms such as hypertension and headaches (Tambağ, 2004) and is positively associated with anxiety and depression (Bridewell & Chang, 1997). Anger-out, on the other

hand, involves directing anger outward toward other people or objects (Karataş, 2009; Saçar, 2007; Spielberger et al., 1995). Individuals with this style openly express anger, often aggressively, believing it helps them influence situations or others (Brondolo et al., 1997). However, frequent externalization of anger can lead to interpersonal difficulties and social isolation (Özmen, 2006). In cases of perceived obstruction or injustice, anger-out behaviors may escalate to aggression (İmamoğlu, 2003). Anger control represents the ability to manage and express anger in a balanced and socially appropriate manner (Karataş, 2009; Saçar, 2007; Spielberger et al., 1995). Individuals with good anger control remain patient and understanding, using problem-solving and communication skills to express their emotions constructively (Özer, 1994a; İmamoğlu, 2003).

Frustration–aggression theory offers an additional explanatory pathway. Digital frustrations—such as disrupted connectivity, unmet social expectations, or online conflict—may elicit frustration that escalates into anger. Conversely, smartphone overuse can create academic, social, or interpersonal problems that generate further frustration. These reciprocal processes highlight the potential for smartphone addiction and anger to reinforce one another. Cognitive–behavioral perspectives further propose that maladaptive cognitions about connectivity, social approval, or threat influence both compulsive smartphone use and anger expression styles. Such cognitions may shape whether adolescents express anger outwardly, suppress it, or engage in attempts at anger control. Taken together, these theoretical perspectives suggest that smartphone addiction, trait anger, and anger expression styles can be interconnected through emotion regulation deficits, reinforcement-based habits, frustration responses, and maladaptive cognitions. Empirical research integrating these frameworks remains limited. Accordingly, the present study examines the relationships among smartphone addiction, trait anger, and anger expression styles in adolescents within a consolidated theoretical context.

Adolescence is a period marked by social, physiological, and psychological transitions, during which individuals prepare for adulthood. In this developmental stage, adolescents tend to display higher levels of anger and aggression compared to other life phases (Steinberg, 2007). Given that adolescents constitute a natural risk group for elevated trait anger and maladaptive anger expression styles, the potential relationship between smartphone addiction, trait anger, and anger expression styles warrants investigation. Therefore, this study aimed to examine the relationship between adolescents' levels of smartphone addiction and their trait anger and anger expression styles. Accordingly, the present study sought to address the following research questions to more comprehensively elucidate the associations among smartphone addiction, trait anger, anger-in, anger-out, and anger control in adolescents:

H1. There is a positive relationship between smartphone addiction and trait anger, anger/in and anger/out.

H2. There is a negative relationship between smartphone addiction and anger control.

METHOD

Research model

The purpose of this research is to examine the relationships between smartphone addiction and the trait anger and anger expression styles of adolescents. The research was designed in a relational design considering that there is a relationship between smartphone addiction level and the trait anger level and anger expression styles of adolescents.

Participants

Firstly, ethical permission was obtained from Eskişehir Osmangazi University Social and Human Sciences Human Research Ethics Committee (Approval number: 2300242011). The population of the study consisted of adolescents enrolled in various high schools in Mersin, Türkiye, during the 2023–2024 academic year. The study sample included students from four different types of high schools located in the same province. The gender distribution of the participants was nearly balanced, with 49.1% male ($n = 350$) and 50.9% female ($n = 363$). The distribution by grade level was as follows: 9th grade: 22.9% ($n = 163$); 10th grade: 28.9% ($n = 206$); 11th grade: 19.2% ($n = 137$); and 12th grade: 29.0% ($n = 207$). The sample selection was made with the convenience sampling method. Data for the study were obtained through face-to-face interactions following the acquisition of informed consent from each participant. Prior to the administration of data collection instruments, comprehensive information was provided regarding the nature of the study, voluntary participation, and the confidentiality of the collected data. Furthermore, participants were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any stage if they wished, and that any information they had provided would subsequently be excluded from the analysis. Only the data of individuals who voluntarily agreed to participate were included in the study. Also since the students who participated in the implementation were under the age of eighteen, a parental consent form was utilized. Parental permission was obtained for all participants included in the study.

Measures

The smartphone addiction scale short version

The Smartphone Addiction Scale Short Version scale, developed by Kwon, Kim, Cho & Yang (2013), was translated into Turkish by Şata and Karip in 2017. This self-report instrument was designed to assess the level of smartphone addiction among adolescents. The scale consists of 10 items rated on a six-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree). The total possible score ranges from 10 to 60, with higher scores indicating higher levels of smartphone addiction. In the current study, the Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficient of the SAS-SV was .83, demonstrating good reliability.

Trait anger and anger expression scales

Trait Anger and Anger Expression Scales, developed by Spielberger (1988), was translated into Turkish by Özer in 1994. Trait Anger and Anger Expression Scales is a four-point Likert-type scale consisting of 34 items. The first 10 items measure trait anger, while the remaining items assess anger expression styles, which include three subscales: Anger-In (internalized anger): Items 13, 15, 16, 20, 23, 26, 27, and 31; Anger-Out (externalized anger): Items 12, 17, 19, 22, 24, 29, 32, and 33; Anger Control: Items 11, 14, 18, 21, 25, 28, 30, and 34. The possible score range for the trait anger subscale is 10–40, while each of the anger expression subscales ranges from 8–32. Higher trait anger scores indicate greater anger intensity. Higher anger-in scores reflect greater suppression of anger. Higher anger-out scores indicate a tendency to express anger outwardly. Higher anger control scores reflect better ability to regulate anger. In this research, Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficient for trait anger scale was calculated as .83, anger-in subscale was calculated as .73, anger-out subscale was calculated as .80 and anger control subscale was calculated as .80.

Demographic information form

This form includes questions about gender, class level, and type of high school. Participants' voluntary consent to participate in the study was obtained using a Demographic Information Form. The form was prepared by the researchers.

Parental consent form

Since participants were under 18 years of age, a Parental Consent Form was used. The study was explained to parents in writing, information about the researchers was provided, and contact details were shared. Parents' wet-ink signatures and necessary personal information were obtained.

Statistical analysis

Before analysis, the numerical data were examined to determine whether they met the assumption of normal

distribution using Skewness and Kurtosis tests, histograms, and Q-Q plots. Outliers were detected using boxplot graphs, leading to the removal of data from 40 participants identified as having extreme, erroneous, or missing values. Consequently, the analyses were performed on data from 713 participants. After cleaning, all variables were found to conform to the assumption of normality. Categorical variables were summarized using frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were presented as means and standard deviations. To examine the relationships between continuous variables, the Pearson correlation test was used. Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$, with analyses performed using SPSS version 24. Results were interpreted according to the following criteria: correlations were considered significant if $p < .05$ and not significant if $p > .05$. The Skewness and Kurtosis values for each variable were as follows: Smartphone Addiction:

Skewness = 0.461, Kurtosis = 0.176. Trait Anger: Skewness = 0.505, Kurtosis = 0.077. Anger-In: Skewness = 0.237, Kurtosis

and negative correlation was found between smartphone addiction and anger control ($r = -.117, p = .002$). These findings indicate that as adolescents' levels of smartphone

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Variables Included in The Study

	N	Mean	SD	Median	Minimum	Maximum
Smartphone Addiction	713	27.32	9.76	27.00	10.00	60.00
Trait Anger	713	21.41	6.08	21.00	10.00	40.00
Anger-In	713	17.64	4.82	17.00	8.00	32.00
Anger-Out	713	16.38	4.80	16.00	8.00	32.00
Anger Control	713	20.09	4.97	20.00	8.00	32.00

= -0.333. Anger-Out: Skewness = 0.746, Kurtosis = 0.417. Anger Control: Skewness = 0.049, Kurtosis = -0.229.

According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2013), data are considered normally distributed when skewness and kurtosis values fall between -1.5 and +1.5. Therefore, the data in this study satisfied the assumption of normality.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for smartphone addiction, trait anger, and anger expression styles (anger-in, anger-out, and anger control). The mean score for the Smartphone Addiction Scale was 27.32 (SD = 9.76), with scores ranging between 10 and 60. For the Trait Anger and Anger Expression Scale, the following mean scores were obtained: Trait Anger: $M = 21.41$ (SD = 6.08). Anger-In: $M = 17.64$ (SD = 4.82). Anger-Out: $M = 16.38$ (SD = 4.80). Anger Control: $M = 20.09$ (SD = 4.97). These results indicate that, on average, adolescents in the study reported moderate levels of smartphone addiction and moderate levels of trait anger and anger expression tendencies.

addiction increase, their trait anger, anger-in, and anger-out scores also increase, while their anger control scores decrease. Based on the results of the correlation analyses, smartphone addiction showed significant positive correlations with trait anger, anger-in, and anger-out. Smartphone addiction showed a significant negative correlation with anger control. In other words, adolescents with higher levels of smartphone addiction tended to exhibit greater anger intensity, higher levels of both internalized and externalized anger, and lower ability to regulate their anger effectively.

DISCUSSION

In this section, the relationship between adolescents' smartphone addiction and trait anger and anger expression styles is discussed and interpreted in light of previous research and relevant theoretical perspectives. The findings of the present study revealed that as adolescents' levels of smartphone addiction increased, their trait anger, anger-in, and anger-out scores also increased, while their anger control scores decreased. This indicates that higher smartphone addiction is

Table 2. Pearson Correlation Coefficients Among Study Variables

	Smartphone Addiction	Trait anger	Anger/In	Anger/Out	Anger Control
Smartphone Addiction	-	.296**	.211**	.276**	-.117*
Trait anger		-	.477**	.665**	-.291**
Anger/In			-	.410**	.131**
Anger/out				-	-.291**
Anger Control					-

Note. r = Pearson correlation coefficient; $p < .05$; $p < .001$

Correlation analysis between smartphone addiction, trait anger, and anger expression styles

The relationships between smartphone addiction, trait anger, anger-in, anger-out, and anger control were analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient. The results are presented in Table 2. As shown in the table, a low but statistically significant positive correlation was found between smartphone addiction and trait anger ($r = .296, p < .001$). Similarly, smartphone addiction was positively correlated with both anger-in ($r = .211, p < .001$) and anger-out ($r = .276, p < .001$). Conversely, a low

associated with greater overall anger intensity and a tendency to express anger in maladaptive ways—either by suppressing it or by expressing it outwardly—along with lower emotional regulation abilities. A review of the existing literature shows that although no previous study has directly examined the relationship between smartphone addiction and anger expression styles in adolescents, several studies report findings that are consistent with these results. For instance, a study conducted with Turkish high school students found that adolescents with home internet access displayed significantly higher anger-in scores than those without access, and that

students who used the internet on their mobile phones exhibited significantly higher anger-in and anger-out scores compared to non-users. Additionally, those who spent more time online scored higher on anger-in than those who spent less time online (Sağay, 2013). Similarly, Aygen and Açıık (2014) reported that adolescents who used alcohol or other addictive substances had significantly higher trait anger, anger-in, and anger-out scores compared to those who did not, suggesting a broader connection between addictive behaviors and maladaptive anger expression.

The present study's finding that increased smartphone addiction is accompanied by elevated trait anger and poorer anger regulation can be interpreted through several behavioral and psychosocial mechanisms. One possible explanation lies in the aggressive and competitive elements of mobile gaming and the exposure to cyberbullying on social media platforms—both of which may amplify anger and hostility in real life. Supporting this interpretation, Erdur Baker and Kavşut (2007) found that both cyberbullying perpetration and victimization rates among adolescents were high, and that the use of internet-based communication networks was positively associated with involvement in cyberbullying. Similarly, Anderson and Dill (2000) demonstrated a significant positive correlation between exposure to violent video games and aggressive thoughts and behaviors among adolescents. These findings collectively suggest that smartphone-related activities may serve as situational triggers for anger and aggression, particularly for adolescents with poor emotional regulation skills.

Another possible mechanism involves withdrawal-like reactions to smartphone deprivation. For individuals with high levels of smartphone dependency, being separated from their device may induce frustration and anger. Supporting this notion, Elhai et al. (2018) found significant positive correlations between smartphone addiction and trait anger, anger-in, and anger-out, when participants were asked to imagine losing their smartphones. The authors argued that smartphone deprivation may evoke strong emotional distress and irritability akin to withdrawal symptoms observed in behavioral addictions. This suggests that the inability to access one's smartphone may temporarily increase state anger and reduce one's capacity for anger control. Furthermore, excessive smartphone use can contribute to impaired emotion regulation through constant overstimulation, reduced face-to-face interaction, and habitual exposure to emotionally charged digital content. These factors may heighten emotional reactivity and reduce tolerance for frustration, leading adolescents to respond with anger more frequently or intensely. Over time, this may foster maladaptive anger expression styles, such as suppressing anger (anger-in) or expressing it impulsively (anger-out), rather than engaging in constructive regulation (anger control).

From a developmental perspective, adolescence is already a period characterized by heightened emotional sensitivity and limited regulatory capacity (Steinberg, 2007). Thus, when the

neurocognitive immaturity of this age group interacts with high smartphone dependency, the risk of emotion dysregulation—and by extension, maladaptive anger expression—may be amplified. The continuous connectivity and instant feedback loops of digital platforms may further reinforce emotional impulsivity, making it more difficult for adolescents to manage their anger in a healthy way. Overall, the findings of this study suggest that smartphone addiction does not merely represent a behavioral dependence on technology but may also be associated with emotional dysregulation manifested through increased anger and decreased control. These findings are consistent with previous research indicating that smartphone addiction correlates positively with negative affect, anxiety, and aggression, and negatively with self-control and well-being (Akaltun, 2020; Dikeç et al., 2020; Seo, 2018; Amez & Bearth, 2020). Taken together, the results of this study underscore the importance of addressing emotional regulation, anger management, and responsible technology use within adolescent mental health and educational interventions. The patterns observed suggest that interventions aimed at reducing smartphone dependency may also indirectly contribute to improving adolescents' anger regulation capacities and overall emotional well-being.

Conclusion

Adolescence represents a critical period of human development characterized by rapid biological, psychological, and social changes. Successfully completing the developmental tasks of this stage is essential for individuals' subsequent adjustment and well-being. Considering that nearly every adolescent today owns a smartphone, examining the psychological and behavioral implications of smartphone use has become increasingly important. The present study investigated the relationships between smartphone addiction, trait anger, and anger expression styles among adolescents. The findings revealed that higher levels of smartphone addiction were significantly and positively correlated with trait anger, anger-in, and anger-out, while negatively correlated with anger control. In other words, adolescents who were more dependent on smartphones tended to experience anger more intensely, were more likely to suppress or externalize their anger, and demonstrated lower ability to regulate it effectively. These results suggest that smartphone addiction is not merely a behavioral issue but is closely associated with emotional regulation difficulties. Excessive smartphone use may disrupt adolescents' capacity to manage anger and other emotions adaptively. This connection can be understood within the broader context of technology's impact on attention, self-control, and interpersonal functioning. The present study is also notable in that it appears to be the first quantitative investigation in Türkiye examining these specific relationships among adolescents. The use of convenience sampling represents a limitation of the study, as both the sample and its size restrict the generalizability of the findings. Because the sample consists solely of Turkish high school students, broader generalization is limited. Future research should include students from diverse

cultural backgrounds and larger samples to enhance external validity. Based on the findings, several practical and research-oriented recommendations can be made: Future studies could employ qualitative or mixed methods to explore adolescents' subjective experiences of smartphone use and anger expression in greater depth. Future quantitative research may examine potential mediators such as internet use purpose, cyberbullying experiences, emotional regulation strategies, or peer relationships in explaining the link between smartphone addiction and anger expression. Schools and families should be encouraged to implement digital literacy and emotion regulation programs aimed at reducing smartphone dependency and promoting healthy anger management strategies among adolescents. Mental health professionals working with adolescents could incorporate smartphone use monitoring and anger management training into preventive counseling programs to reduce the risk of emotional dysregulation.

Consent to participate: Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study. In addition, permission was obtained from their parents.

Ethical approval: The study was performed in accordance with the ethical standards laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its following updates. Ethical permission was obtained from Eskişehir Osmangazi University Social and Human Sciences Human Research Ethics Committee (Approval number: 2300242011).

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